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Research Article

**LIPOPROTEIN REDUCTION IN PATIENTS WITH
CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES**¹Dr. Muhammad Ghufuran, ²Dr. Almas Hassan, ³Dr. Ali Ahmed Ranjha²MBBS; Nawaz Sharif Medical College Gujrat, Pakistan^{1,3}MBBS; King Edward Medical University, Lahore, Pakistan.**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Lipoprotein(a) (Lp(a)) is an LDL-like molecule containing an apolipoprotein B-100 (apo(B-100)) particle locked by a disulphide bridge to apo(a). Cardiovascular diseases cause 3% of all deaths in North America being the foremost common explanation for death in European men under 65 years of aged and therefore the second most common cause in women. **Method:** 256 patients were blindly randomized. Patients got the hepatocyte-directed antisense oligonucleotide AKCEA-APO(a)-LRx, named to here as APO(a)-LRx, or saline placebo subcutaneously for six to 12 months. **Results:** dose dependent mean percent reductions in lipoprotein(a) from baseline were noticed, with decreases of 46% at a dose of 20 mg every 4 weeks, 66% at 40 mg every 4 weeks, 58% at 20 mg every 2 weeks, 82% at 60 mg every 4 weeks, and 89% at 20 mg every week, as compared with 9% for the pooled placebo group (P value range for the comparison with placebo, 0.003 to <0.001). The two regimens of the same monthly dose (40 mg) — 40 mg every 4 weeks and 20 mg every 2 weeks — lessened lipoprotein(a) to similar extents. **Conclusion:** Lipoprotein(a) levels were lowered by APO(a)-LRx in a dose-dependent manner in patients who had elevated lipoprotein(a) levels and established cardiovascular disease.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) in North America cause 3% of all deaths (1). It is the most common cause of death in European men under the age of 65 years and the second most common cause in women (2). Lipoprotein(a) is an LDL-like molecule containing an apolipoprotein B-100 (apo(B-100)) particle attached by a disulphide link to apo(a). Many researches have proved that high level of lipoprotein is a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. These facts recommended us to think about new strategies for prediction, prevention, and treatment of cardiovascular disease. In the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis and its complications inflammatory mechanisms play a major role (3).

It has been displayed that atherogenic lipoproteins such as apo(B-100), oxidized low-density lipoprotein (LDL), remnant lipoprotein (beta-VLDL), and lipoprotein(a) offer a critical role in the proinflammatory reaction (4). Lp(a) performs by inhibiting the activation of transforming growth factor (TGF) and participating to the growth of arterial atherosclerotic lesions by enhancing the proliferation of vascular smooth muscle cells and the transfer of smooth muscle cells to endothelial cells. Moreover at the surfaces of endothelial cells Lp(a) inhibits plasminogen binding and decreases the activity of fibrin-dependent tissue-type plasminogen activator (5). Lp(a) may behave as a proinflammatory mediator that intensifies the lesion formation in atherosclerotic plaques. An independent predictor of coronary artery disease and myocardial infarction is elevated serum Lp(a) (6).

Composition of Lipoprotein(a) is of a low-density lipoprotein (LDL)-like moiety bound covalently to apolipoprotein(a) (7). Lipoprotein(a) potentially contributes to cardiovascular disease through proatherogenic effects of its LDL-like moiety, proinflammatory effects of its oxidized phospholipid content, and prothrombotic effects through its inactive, plasminogen-like protease domain on apolipoprotein(a) (8).

In some studies, Lp(a) particles are prone to oxidation and that the increased risk of coronary artery disease is related with elevated Lp(a) levels may be related in part to their oxidative modification (9). The oxidative type of Lp(a) (ox-Lp(a)) might diminish fibrinolytic activity through the depletion of plasminogen activation, might prompt PAI-1 production in vascular endothelial cells, and might retard endothelium-dependent vasodilation (10).

It has been showed that glycation enhances the production of PAI-1 and attenuates the production of t-PA inherited by Lp(a) in arterial and venous

endothelial cells (EC). The emergence of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs) and EC-mediated oxidative modification may accord the changing of the generation of PAI-1 and t-PA induced by glycated Lp(a). The combination of hyperglycaemia and hyper lipoprotein(a) may decrease EC-derived fibrinolytic activity, which may promote the development of thrombosis and atherosclerosis in subjects with diabetes (11).

No pharmacologic therapies have been approved yet that specifically target lipoprotein(a). The inhibition of the production of apolipoprotein(a) in the hepatocyte, the source of approximately 99% of plasma lipoprotein (is assisted by Antisense oligonucleotides (ASOs) (12). Preclinical proof-of-concept studies have established that ASOs specifically reduce plasma levels of lipoprotein(a) by targeting hepatic LPA messenger RNA (mRNA) (13). Subsequent phase 1 and 2 studies of a non-hepatocyte-targeted, second-generation ASO showed lowering of lipoprotein(a) levels in healthy participants who had elevated lipoprotein(a), as well as in patients with established cardiovascular disease and elevated plasma levels of lipoprotein (14). Advances in directing ASOs to hepatocytes by conjugation with a triantennary N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc3) moiety, have resulted in large increases (by a factor of 15 to 30) in their potency, with implications for improvements in the side effect profile and safety of ASOs (15). AKCEA APO(a)-LRx — here referred to as APO(a)-LRx and previously called IONIS-APO(a)-LRx — is a GalNAc3-conjugated 2'-methoxyethyl chimeric second-generation ASO drug targeted to LPA mRNA. In patients with elevated lipoprotein (a) levels APO(a)-LRx was shown to result in a dose-dependent reduction of 66 to 92% in circulating lipoprotein(a). The long half-life of APO(a)-LRx (approximately 1 month) prompted us to consider longer dosing intervals in the trial we report here. (16)

METHODS:

It is a randomized controlled trial (RCT) study. We conducted randomized, dose-ranging, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to evaluate APO(a)-LRx. Five groups have been made randomly, within each group, randomization was performed in a 5:1 ratio (APO(a)-LRx: placebo). Patients who were 18 to 80 years of age and had established cardiovascular disease and an elevated screening plasma lipoprotein(a) level (≥ 60 mg per decilitre [150 nmol per liter]), and the patients who were being treated with lipid-lowering medications could be enrolled. However, patients with acute coronary syndrome, major cardiac surgery, or stroke or transient ischemic attack within 6 months before screening; coronary, carotid, or peripheral revascularization, major no cardiac surgery, or

lipoprotein apheresis within 3 months before screening; were excluded.

The patients in each group were given one of five regimens, for a minimum of 6 months, APO(a)-LRx or placebo administered subcutaneously: APO(a)-LRx every 4 weeks at a dose of 20 mg, every 4 weeks 40 mg, every 4 weeks 60 mg, 20 mg every 2 weeks, or 20 mg every week or physiologic saline placebo. By week 25, the groups receiving monthly doses would have reached 6 months of exposure (after the week 21 dose); however, the groups receiving doses every 2 weeks or every week would have reached only 5.5 and 5.75 months of exposure, respectively. Therefore, the timing of the analysis of the primary efficacy end point was moved to week 27 for these groups.

To collect effective and safety data, site visits were scheduled to occur every 4 weeks. Throughout the treatment period, in every 2 weeks platelet counts and renal-function tests were performed and liver function tests were performed every 2 weeks for the first 3 months and monthly thereafter. Simultaneously both central and local laboratories were used to analyse platelet count, and APO(a)-LRx or placebo could be administered only if recent (within 14 days) platelet-count results were available. Monitoring and stopping rules included threshold limits on platelet count and renal and liver function. The protocol was approved by the relevant health authorities, institutional review boards, and ethics committees.

All efficacy analyses were performed with the full analysis set, defined as all patients who had undergone randomization and had received at least one dose of APO(a)-LRx or placebo. The primary end point and secondary end points for oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein B, oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein(a) (17), LDL cholesterol, and apolipoprotein B were examined by using covariance model with treatment groups as factors and the log-transformed baseline value for each respective measure as covariate. A logistic regression model with the log-transformed baseline level of lipoprotein(a) as the concomitant variable was used to perform responder analyses. A multiple-imputation model containing baseline and post baseline values, was used to handle the missing data and were stratified according to treatment group. Because of the exploratory nature of this study, the P values and widths of the 95% confidence intervals were not adjusted for multiplicity. All safety analyses were performed in the safety population, defined as all patients who underwent randomization and received at least one dose of APO(a)-LRx or placebo.

RESULTS:

Of the 324 patients who went through eligibility assessment, 256 were assigned to one of five

APO(a)-LRx regimens or placebo randomly. The first patient was randomized on December 17, 2018, and the last patient underwent randomization on February 26, 2020.

The mean ($\pm$ SD) duration of treatment was 31.6 ± 11.5 weeks (median, 32.1) between patients who have taken APO(a)-LRx and 31.2 ± 12.0 weeks (median, 34.0) among those who received placebo. Approximately 60% of patients were less than 65 years, and more than 30% were women. By protocol design, all patients had confirmed atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, most commonly coronary artery disease; 4.5% of the patients had both carotid and peripheral artery disease.

In each group almost 45% patients had premature coronary artery disease. Most of patients reported family history of coronary artery disease, and approximately one third had familial hypercholesterolemia. Approximately 80 to 90% of the patients were receiving statin therapy at trial entry, 50% were having ezetimibe, and 20% were taking a PCSK9 inhibitor.

At baseline across all groups, median levels of lipoprotein(a) ranged from 205 to 247 nmol per liter (the upper limit of the normal range is 40 mg per decilitres [75 nmol per liter]), 13 median levels of oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein B ranged from 21.3 to 24.6 nmol per liter (the top quartile in the general population is >9 nmol per liter), and median levels of oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein(a) ranged from 56.9 to 63.3 nmol per liter (the top quartile in the general population is >20 nmol per liter). The mean levels of LDL cholesterol were ranging from 67.6 to 89.3 mg per decilitre (1.75 to 2.31 mmol per liter). Mean estimated corrected LDL cholesterol levels ranged from 41.8 to 54.4 mg per decilitre, if it is thought that 30% of lipoprotein(a) mass is cholesterol.

At 6 months of exposure (25 or 27 weeks), in all the APO(a)-LRx groups, dose dependent mean percent reductions in lipoprotein(a) from baseline were noticed, with decreases of 46% at a dose of 20 mg every 4 weeks, 66% at 40 mg every 4 weeks, 58% at 20 mg every 2 weeks, 82% at 60 mg every 4 weeks, and 89% at 20 mg every week, as compared with 9% for the pooled placebo group (P value range for the comparison with placebo, 0.003 to <0.001). The two regimens of the same monthly dose (40 mg) — 40 mg every 4 weeks and 20 mg every 2 weeks — lowered lipoprotein(a) to similar extents.

The lowering effect of lipoprotein(a) was noted within the first month and reached near-maximal effect by week 16. In addition, in all the APO(a)-

LRx groups, dose-dependent absolute reductions in lipoprotein(a) levels were observed. The lipoprotein(a) levels came back to baseline within 16 weeks after the last dose.

In 90% of patients receiving APO(a)-LRx and in 83% of those receiving placebo during the treatment period adverse events occurred; were mild or moderate. Serious adverse events occurred in 10% of the patients receiving APO(a)-LRx and in 2% of those receiving placebo. Neither the overall occurrence of adverse events nor the incidence of serious events reported a dose-dependent pattern. Overall, 5% of patients who took APO(a)-LRx and 4% of those who received placebo left the trial due to adverse events. Myalgia or arthralgia were the most common adverse events causing discontinuation among patients who received APO(a)-LRx. No patients discontinued participation for protocol-defined reasons. In 23% of the patients who received APO(a)-LRx and in 8% of those who received placebo during the trial, injection-site reaction was the most frequently reported adverse event. Irrespective of the dose regimen approximately 8% of injections were associated with injection-site reactions. These reactions were mostly mild, and the most frequent was erythema (26%).

Other adverse events that occurred in more than 10% of patients who received APO(a)-LRx and were more frequent than in the placebo group were urinary tract infection (15% vs. 7%), myalgia (14% vs. 11%), and headache (13% vs. 9%). The influenza-like symptoms were similar in the APO(a)-LRx group and the placebo group (8% and 7%, respectively). Platelet count monitoring that was conducted every 2 weeks did not reveal a dose- or time-dependent effect of APO(a)-LR, and no patient had a platelet count lower than 100,000 per cubic millimetre. No patient had liver or renal toxic effects that met the predetermined thresholds for treatment discontinuation. There were no clinically significant changes in other laboratory measures (including coagulation panel), vital signs, or electrocardiographic measures. High sensitivity C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were measured as a safety outcome to gauge potential proinflammatory effects of APO(a)-LRx. Baseline high-sensitivity CRP levels were between 2 and 3 mg per liter across the groups (Table 1). The absolute mean changes in the high-sensitivity CRP level at 6 months of exposure were -0.8 ± 5.2 mg per liter in the group that received 20 mg every 4 weeks, -0.8 ± 4.2 mg per liter in the group that received 40 mg every 4 weeks, -0.4 ± 2.8 mg per liter in the group that received 20 mg every 2 weeks, -0.5 ± 2.8 mg per liter in the group that received 60 mg every 4 weeks, and -0.2 ± 5.8 mg per liter in the group that received 20 mg every week, as compared with

-0.8 ± 5.2 mg per liter in the pooled placebo group. Two deaths occurred during the trial, both in patients receiving APO(a)-LRx.

DISCUSSION:

Evidence from studies of primary prevention showed that elevated lipoprotein(a) levels are related with an increased atherothrombotic risk — in particular, an increased risk of myocardial infarction (19).

The role of lipoprotein(a) in the context of secondary prevention remains disputed. Furthermore, a recent analysis of data from the placebo group in the FOURIER trial reported that irrespective of LDL cholesterol levels, higher levels of lipoprotein(a) are connected with an increased risk of cardiovascular events in patients with established cardiovascular disease(20).

Lipoprotein(a) is the highest-capacity carrier of oxidized phospholipids, among lipoproteins, which are reason for most of its proinflammatory effects. In our trial, dose-dependent reductions were noticed in oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein B and oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein(a) in plasma.

In past studies, oxidized phospholipids on apolipoprotein B, primarily reflecting the oxidized phospholipid content of lipoprotein(a), predicted first and recurrent myocardial infarction, stroke, and aortic stenosis(21). The reduction in LDL cholesterol and apolipoprotein B levels by ASOs targeting LPA mRNA, in the presence of aggressive lipid-lowering therapy, has been documented in previous studies. Such findings may indicate that, when the synthesis of apolipoprotein(a) is inhibited in the liver, apolipoprotein B lipoproteins — which would otherwise be destined to become lipoprotein(a), with relatively low plasma clearance as a result of weak interactions with the LDL receptor — are converted to LDL particles with relatively strong affinity for the LDL receptor and hence a relatively quick and efficient clearance from the blood(22).

We did not observe marked changes in platelet, renal, or liver function, nor a between-group difference in the risk of influenza-like symptoms. The most common adverse events among patients who received APO(a)-LRx were injection site reactions, which were generally mild. Elevated levels of lipoprotein(a) are a cardiovascular risk factor for which no effective pharmacological therapy currently exists. In this trial, we found that APO(a)-LRx provided potent reductions in levels of lipoprotein(a) in patients with cardiovascular disease.

CONCLUSION:

Lp(a) mainly derived from its role as a cardiovascular risk factor. Although not taken as an established risk factor, Lp(a) levels have been related with cardiovascular disease many studies. Recently Lp(a) serum levels were taken to be associated with the severity of aortic atherosclerosis, commonly in abdominal aorta, as well as coronary atherosclerosis.

Moreover Lp(a) is implicated in the activation of endothelial uptake, oxidative modification, and foam cell formation, proposing that these processes could perform an important character in atherosclerosis. Current findings suggest that Lp(a)-lowering therapy might be favourable, at least in some subgroups of patients with high Lp(a) levels(23).

A study by Momiyama *et al.* demonstrated that increased Lp(a) level has additional prognostic value in symptomatic patients with coronary artery revascularization. Lp(a) is included in the evolution of atherothrombosis and activation of acute inflammation deploying a proatherogenic and hypofibrinolytic effect(24).

In future therapeutic approach could comprise apheresis in high-risk patients with already supremely lowered LDL cholesterol levels in order to reduce major coronary events. However, further studies are required to define such subgroups with regard to Lp(a) levels, apo(a) size, and the presence of other risk factors.

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